
How to hire the best people

Steve Jobs was obsessed with hiring “the best people.” You should be too.

- **They don’t need to be managed.**
 - **They are lifelong learners.**
 - **They take risks and embrace failure.**
 - **They radiate passion.**
 - **They argue passionately but admit when they’re wrong.**
 - **They embrace Bayesian thinking.**
 - **They own their mistakes.**
 - **They are artists in their craft.**
 - **They simplify chaos.**
 - **They don’t settle for “good enough.”**
 - **They are driven but empathetic.**
 - **They value collaboration.**
 - **They avoid micromanagement.**
 - **They attract talent.**
 - **They embrace diversity.**
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I have always believed that, as a research leader or institution, the most critical decisions we make are about hiring. Bringing the right people into the team can create a ripple effect of benefits, amplifying positive impacts across the lab, the institution, and even the broader research community. These individuals not only contribute directly but also foster an environment of collaboration, innovation, and mutual support that elevates everyone’s work. Conversely, hiring problematic individuals can have a corrosive impact, introducing stress, tension, and conflict that disrupt productivity and morale, often extending far beyond their immediate surroundings. Careful and thoughtful hiring is not just about filling a role—it is about shaping the culture, vision, and long-term success of the team and institution.

[The Sainsbury Lab. November 2024.](#)

Hiring decisions carry long-lasting consequences

The people you bring into your team do far more than simply fill roles; they drive projects, create opportunities, and influence the culture of your institution. Yet, many leaders approach hiring as if it were a routine administrative task—a box-ticking exercise rather than the high-stakes decision it truly is. I'm often astonished at the casual approach some take to recruitment: post an ad for a few weeks, interview the top applicants, and make an offer. While this can work in some cases, more often than not, the limited timeframe and narrow outreach mean you're missing out on truly exceptional talent. These hiring decisions carry long-lasting consequences, shaping not only the immediate success of a team but also the trajectory of projects, departments, and even careers—especially when recruiting for faculty positions or leadership roles.

Skills are overrated

Another issue I often see in recruitment is an overemphasis on skills. Of course, skills are important, but they're just one part of the equation. Hiring solely based on skills is shortsighted. [I've long argued against hyperspecialization for this reason.](#) The best people we've recruited over the years are undoubtedly skilled, but they're also flexible, curious, and [willing to learn and step out of their comfort zones.](#) They adapt and evolve alongside the science, learning new things and tackling challenges in innovative ways. In my view, skills are often overrated in recruitment, especially in well-rounded environments where expertise is abundant and opportunities for growth are readily available to anyone with the drive to learn. Trust me, you don't want to hire the proverbial person with a hammer who sees every

problem as a nail. It's the ability to think broadly, adapt, and contribute creatively that truly elevates a team.

“If all you have is a hammer, everything looks like a nail.” Source: [ChatGPT](#).

Hire people who never stop learning

Hiring people with the right mindset—a willingness to learn, improve, and grow—is far more important than simply hiring for skills. Ambition and motivation to develop are qualities that outshine technical expertise in the long run. [I'd much rather recruit a predoctoral student](#) with limited skills but the right attitude and eagerness to learn than a self-satisfied postdoc who has stopped seeking growth. Nothing frustrates me more than a sense of entitlement, especially in young students and early career researchers. If you're a 19-year-old at a prestigious university, congratulations—you've achieved something remarkable so far. But let's be clear: you haven't "made it." Your journey of learning and growth is just beginning. In fact, the moment you think you've "made it," you're finished—because growth stops the instant complacency sets in.

Do you think you've "made it"

I remember a colleague asking me years ago, "So, how does it feel now that you've made it?" The question caught me off guard because I've never seen my career as a destination towards a point of arrival. My work is an ongoing journey, constantly changing and evolving. Yes, there have been moments of success, but they were just milestones—not endpoints. The very concept of "making it" makes me cringe; it feels static, as if one becomes a passive beneficiary of the efforts of others, a parasite on both employers and society.

If you think differently—if you believe you've "made it" and that success is now your entitlement—then good luck to you, but I don't want you on my team. I want people who see success as a starting point for new challenges, not as an excuse to rest on their laurels.

But how do you actually spot exceptional talent?

I was recently reminded of the importance of recruitment decisions when I came across a post on X (formerly Twitter) by [@thePhilRivers](#), discussing [how Steve Jobs was famously obsessed with hiring "the best people."](#) The thread outlined 10 non-obvious signals to identify high performers, and it struck a chord with me.

[Steve Jobs was famously obsessed with hiring "the best people."](#)

Exceptional people bring qualities that go far beyond technical expertise—they embody traits that elevate not only themselves but everyone around them. Here's what I look for, inspired by [@thePhilRivers](#) post:

- **They don't need to be managed.** Once they understand the goal and vision, they take ownership and run with it.
- **They are lifelong learners.** They actively seek out knowledge, teaching themselves and refusing to adopt a passive attitude toward learning.

- **They take risks and embrace failure.** They understand that achieving greatness requires bold decisions and the occasional misstep.

Michael Fischbach @mfgrp · Apr 11

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3) Don't avoid risk; befriend it. A useful starting point for evaluating a new idea is to place it on the graph below. We will consider the axes one at a time. 11/53

Don't avoid risk; befriend it. /via Michael Fischbach [@mfgrp](#) [How to pick a problem.](#)

- **They radiate passion.** Their eyes light up when discussing the future, and as a leader, your job is to inspire them to channel that passion toward the collective goal.
- **They argue passionately but admit when they're wrong.** They thrive on heated debates but are unafraid to change their stance when evidence proves them wrong.
- **They embrace Bayesian thinking.** They update their priors as new evidence emerges.
- **They own their mistakes.** Saying "I'm wrong" is never taboo for them—it's a step toward improvement.

The importance of wrong

- Our goal is to generate robust knowledge to advance science
- “I was wrong” should not be taboo
- Respond quickly, admit error, make correction

[“I was wrong should not be taboo.”](#)

- **They are artists in their craft.** Whether they’re designing, coding, or leading, they refine and perfect their work until it’s “insanely great.”
- **They simplify chaos.** They have a knack for breaking down complexity, knowing that simplicity often demands the most creativity and clarity.
- **They don’t settle for “good enough.”** Achieving greatness only fuels their hunger for more, keeping them driven and focused.
- **They are driven but empathetic.** They mentor others with care, understanding the value of team success over individual glory.

[The Importance of empathy. Watch the video.](#)

- **They value collaboration.** They recognize they can’t succeed alone and work to earn the trust and respect of their colleagues.

- **They avoid micromanagement.** Just as they resist being micromanaged, they wouldn't subject others to it.
- **They attract talent.** Their energy and achievements make them magnets for other exceptional people, creating a cycle of inspiration and recruitment.
- **They embrace diversity.** They understand that success stems from diverse perspectives, not homogeneity. As Steve Jobs could have said, "[A team of 11 Lionel Messis will not win the World Cup.](#)" They know that the best teams blend strengths and skills to innovate and solve complex problems creatively.

TEAM

T ogether
E veryone
A chieves
M ore

[TEAM—Together. Everyone. Achieves. More.](#)

Steve Jobs did famously say, “It doesn’t make sense to hire smart people and then tell them what to do; we hire smart people so they can tell us what to do.” This captures the essence of great hiring: finding individuals who not only fit into your team but elevate it. The best hires are those who challenge assumptions, contribute fresh ideas, and push the team to new heights. Decisions in a high-performing team shouldn’t be unilateral; they should emerge from collaborative discussions, fostering a shared sense of responsibility among everyone, including the leader.

But hiring “the best people” is only the start. Retaining them requires cultivating an environment where they can thrive. Provide opportunities for growth, acknowledge their achievements, and ensure they feel valued and connected to the team’s purpose. Even the most talented individuals will disengage in a toxic or stagnant environment.

The right people don’t just execute a vision—they amplify it, inspiring greatness in those around them. So, take the time to identify them, support them, and create the conditions for them to flourish. The rewards will resonate far beyond your team. Now, go out there and find them!

Acknowledgements

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	URGENT	NOT URGENT
IMPORTANT	Quadrant I urgent and important DO	Quadrant II not urgent but important PLAN
NOT IMPORTANT	Quadrant III urgent but not important DELEGATE	Quadrant IV not urgent and not important ELIMINATE

[Time management for academics.](#)